

EPIGENETIC MUTATION IN ANIMALS: DISCUSSION IN RELATION TO THE MOST SIGNIFICANT PROBLEMS OF THE 20TH AND 21ST CENTURIES

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ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the topic of epigenetic mutation in animals, aiming to broaden the discussion in relation to the most significant problems of the 20th and 21st centuries, regarding the anthropogenic effects on the Environment and how this has affected the lives of animals. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it highlights an argument that is necessary in academia and important as a starting point for research into pollution and the weakening of marine biomes. The target object of study chosen to guide the discussion were sea turtles, due to the fact that the two co-authors, Veterinary Medicine academics, research these animals and their behavioral changes that have occurred, as well as pathologies that have arisen in recent times that still remain without a clinical explanation. The difficulty in establishing controlled studies based on contamination with such metals and empirical observation of their effects, in the laboratory, means that studies at the field level are considered as always inconclusive, a ploy to defend industrial conglomerates that continue to pollute the bays, the reefs and the corals. Darwin (2015) stated that the most adaptive species or individuals are those that survive in nature. This has become a powerful jargon that little or no reflection is made on the complex animal kingdom. But what about those who don't adapt: they simply succumb to chaos? Node! And, as already discussed above, they join the most adaptive and, together, produce stronger generations with greater resilience to the negative impacts of physical and anthropogenic action on the environment. Human action, which causes drastic changes in environments, has been the cause of epigenetic mutations in animals that are interpreted as true aberrations.

Keywords: Epigenetic mutation. Sea turtles. Heavy metal poisoning. Marine biomes.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most prominent problems that the 20th century faced and that the 21st century is facing is that of reconciling economic development with sustainability, for the simple fact that a concept for this term has not yet been created. In addition, there is the issue of not wanting to discuss the promotion of methods of exploitation of natural resources linked to sustainable development. The discussion is complex, given that the agent that could mediate it, namely the State, is the main person responsible for the majority of ecological and environmental disasters that occur, which means that the Private Sector does not follow strict safety standards and uses the most absurd justifications available. For example, when a sea turtle is caught in a fishing net, that is not exactly what happened; it got tangled in the net that, as far as we know, was not intended for its capture; in other words, if it had avoided that fishing area, it would not have suffered any harm. It is the animal's fault.

In the same proportion, there is the issue of pathologies that attack these animals that, until very recently, were not found in them. There are many who say that the exponential increase in recorded cases of fatal diseases in sea turtles is due to the fact that more diagnostic tests are now being performed and also due to greater knowledge about the causes. This argument is dismantled at the first stroke, because there are countless autopsies performed on these animals in laboratories around the world and, given the possibility of communication, it is clear that some diseases have been emerging in recent years, as a result of the exposure of marine and aquatic environments to certain products, which were developed on known dates and, coincidentally, soon after their widespread use, changes in the animals' behavior and the appearance of certain diseases began to be noticed.

The second claim is ridiculous, because it suggests that it is the knowledge of doctors and scientists that causes diseases to appear, while their knowledge only determines their ability to diagnose, positive or negative, a given pathology; which does not dispense with accurate investigation into the problem, in order to know whether we are dealing with a known disease or a mutation of a pathogenic agent.

The disorderly population growth and the consequent occupation of coastal areas, as a mechanism to facilitate trade, has led to a situation of chaos in terms of marine fauna and flora. "Currently, around 50% of the world's population lives in 5% of the planet's emerged area, mainly occupying coastal regions, and this extremely fragile ecosystem is already showing signs of decay. Due to this careless mode of occupation and development, it ended up generating global socio-environmental impacts, which, due to their dimension and severity,

force everyone to learn a new, radical and different way of relating – whether with others, with their own being, with the environment” (ABREU, 2023, p. 127).

In the specific case of sea turtles, the target of this essay, the hypothesis that is being put forward is that it is the contaminated environment that is causing harm to the health of the animals, directly, or whether this polluted environment is contaminating the food they consume and thus causing pathological disorders; which further complicates the situation of these animals, because this would delay a possible environmental adaptation, since their morbidities are caused by indirect causes.

CAPACITY OF ADAPTABILITY OF LIVING BEINGS: WHAT IS CONVENTIONALLY CALLED THE EVOLUTION OF SPECIES

The longer the life expectancy of a living being, the longer it will take for it to evolve in order to become resistant to an environment that is hostile to itself and its species. This is because the adaptive process, which is configured as an evolution of the species, occurs through phylogenetic development and, in many cases, what is observed in terms of a greater tolerance to certain agents that are aggressive to beings, is an ontogenetic process, and is not capable of responding to a need on a global zoological scale, because the environmental pressures of a given location may not occur in other regions and, even if an animal specimen that has evolved for any reason mates, the gene that was previously dominant in the introduced specimen, over time and due to the lack of need for its species preservation factors, will become recessive and will not be destroyed, because in Biology, no acquired characteristic disappears from the genetic code of the species; It just remains in a state of quiescence, manifesting itself according to changes in the environment, which may be an indication that, somewhere nearby, or in that specific *habitat*, some abnormal activity is causing changes in the environment, even before researchers can realize it and the Environment manifests it imminently.

Polluted environments with high levels of heavy metal contamination, especially the most well-known and common ones (cadmium, lead, tin, selenium) tend to cause drastic changes in animals and chronic diseases, such as cancer and others. This is not exactly because they contaminate the environments in which these animals live, which is only half true about their influence on the process. However, they contaminate the food these animals consume, such as seaweed, plankton and even other organisms with shorter life cycles. This is where the issue of direct contamination will cause real harm to turtles, because when they consume

specimens contaminated with these materials, they accumulate directly in the intestine, releasing loads of toxins that will be systematically assimilated by the entire organism.

Among these metals, lead and tin are known to cause bone cancer and bone deterioration, which may well cause changes in the osteomolecular structure of sea turtles, leaving the pseudo-impression that we are facing a process of biological evolution of the species. It is worth clarifying that mutations caused, *a fortiori*, by situations and occurrences of an anthropic nature and other aberrations cannot be considered as evolution, because nature always provides transformations of an aesthetic nature.

The difficulty in establishing controlled studies based on contamination with such metals and empirical observation of their effects in the laboratory means that field studies are always considered inconclusive, a ploy used to defend industrial conglomerates that continue to pollute bays, reefs and corals. Only through controlled studies can we have a more reliable approximation of the harmful effects of contaminating materials, such as those mentioned above. This is a fact, because it would be possible to determine whether the contamination occurs directly, simply through direct contact of the animal with the product dissolved in its natural environment, or whether it occurs through the consumption of contaminated food, which can be deduced as indirect contamination and, therefore, all local marine fauna would be prone to the same fate, given that the flora of this space becomes the agent that spreads the disease itself.

A complex phenomenon occurs, and it is almost impossible to understand it if analyzed in a hasty manner, which is the development of resistance skills to environments that are unhealthy for life. For the hasty, this is about evolution, which it is not, because as Darwin rightly argued, what characterizes an evolutionary process in a given species is the principle of generality, that is, all animals found in that same latitude and longitude range will undergo the same change in their behavior or body structure. "For Darwin, geographic areas could provide nothing more than temporary balances for their inhabitants. Thus, species composed of individuals that are always different from each other (even if slightly) would be, for the naturalist, dynamic units" (SILVA and DUARTE, 2016, p. 433).

If so, what then happens to these animals?

The answer is the occurrence of an *epigenetic mutation*, that is, a non-structural change in the organism, precisely because it has nowhere to go other than the place where it was taken over by the polluting violence. This change is not permanent and, very possibly, when the external agent that causes such refractory endogenous action is attenuated or eliminated, this developed characteristic will disappear, not from the animal's organism, but because its brain

has learned to produce such substances as a natural defense mechanism, as a way of preserving the species.

This is called *adaptability*, and it was on this issue that Charles Darwin devoted most of his research, going so far as to say that it was not the evolution of species that was largely responsible for the maintenance of life; but rather the ability of some members of each species to adapt to the conditions of existence. In his time, the Master could go no further than to speculate about species based on what he had observed around the world.

One detail is that not all members of each species naturally have this ability to develop protein chains that allow them to survive in environments hostile to their species. This characteristic is attributed, by nature, to a very few members, so rare that the structure of their DNA chain is not similar to that of their fellow species.

Thus, when a phenomenon occurs that puts a *species at risk of extinction*, these individuals, with different DNA, are sought out by females in order to mate and, with this, increase the population resistant to the strange and harmful element to the species under imminent threat.

Thus, it can be deduced that human action is not powerful enough to extinguish a species; because nature has already anticipated it in many cases. However, hunger can exterminate a species and this is where man plays his most important role; because when the food source on which other animal species are sustained is eliminated or becomes scarce to drastic levels, there is such an imbalance that it can lead to a catastrophe, of artificial cause, which is grotesquely classified as natural.

Even so, before definitive extinction occurs, many species manage to change their eating habits, which allows them to preserve themselves and this acquired or developed characteristic is passed on to the next generation, giving rise to specimens that are more resistant to the adversities caused by human action on the Environment.

Thus, Darwin (2015) stated that the most adaptive species or individuals are those that survive in nature. This has become a powerful jargon that little or no reflection is made on the complex animal kingdom. But what about those that do not adapt: do they simply succumb to chaos? No! And, as already argued above, they join the most adaptive ones and, together, produce stronger generations with greater resilience to the negative impacts of physical and human action on the Environment.

Nature, already aware that evolution would take a long time to occur, created an adaptation mechanism that works just as well and with a functional, pragmatic response for the species, thus ensuring its survival. This condition can be more easily observed in insects and

mites, because their life cycle is very short when compared to the human life cycle, for example, taking here the maxim of Protagoras of Abdera, that *man is the measure of all things* ; that is, everything in existence and in nature is measured based on human existence. A classic example is that of the fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*), the main pest of corn and which, due to the excessive use of pesticides in its fight, has become polyphagous; *Zea mays* , which was its main source of food, with arguments that it was the only one; However, in order to preserve itself, it developed the ability to consume other plant species (grasses and legumes), varying with the region where there was a greater abundance of each, namely, where crop rotation was carried out with soybeans, it began to attack soybeans; where there are *brachiaria pastures* around corn plantations, it began to attack pasture areas. It adapted according to the situation.

Silva and Duarte (2016) argue that “epigenetic mutations occur in a very different way from genetic mutations. They are the product of the silencing or activation of a gene and not of the change in the order of nitrogenous bases; they only turn genes on and off. Furthermore, epigenetic mutations are always directed, responding to changes in the environment. Some forms of epigenetic mutation can be passed on to offspring, functioning as a genetic mutation; but, unlike the latter, they can be reversible” (SILVA and DUARTE, 2016, p. 438-9).

Epigenetic mutation will not cause changes in the structure of an individual's DNA; it is a chain of proteins that is produced with the purpose of adapting this same being to stressful situations to such an extreme that, hypothetically, it could put the entire [*or almost the entire*] population studied at risk. Thus, this would be a survival strategy for the species to face the occasional bad weather that threatens the planet's biomes, with or without human interference. This undefined being acts as an accelerator of the processes of biological adaptation, because, as it does not have a place in nature, it needs to adapt it to its limited adaptability conditions, which causes specific biomes to be modified and also contaminated with the residues of its actions. *Anthropogenic action* literally means, in a semantic sense, an activity caused by someone who does not have a place in nature; by definition, by man. In this modification, the entire natural state is altered, influencing native life in a negative way. And these same biological changes observed in species that inhabit certain biomes cannot be observed in the same species that live in different biomes, simply because, given the conditions of influence, such changes did not occur. Darwin must have made such observations in order to defend his thesis of natural evolution with such emphasis on geographical parameters as determinants.

To argue that “what is currently being called 'epigenetic mutation' is a set of phenomena that could be at the origin of many diseases and disturbances in natural species” (SILVA and DUARTE, 2016, p. 439) is to demonstrate total ignorance about it, because its occurrence does

not cause any type of pathology; on the contrary, the intention is for the organism to become resistant to the variations that occur in nature due to anthropic actions, such as excessive pollution with toxic materials that contaminate water, soil and micro and macro organisms that make up the fauna and flora, serving as food for other species.

Until the animals already existing in this ecosystem adapt to the new cruel and degrading reality, many anomalies will arise and cause aberrations for which the native species were not prepared, resulting in diseases of all kinds and, in many cases, can also infect humans, since they, in some cases, consume meat, derivatives and other products from these animals. Therefore, protecting natural environments against predatory and destructive actions is a matter of survival for an entire biological chain. Animals and their misunderstood symptoms are just a thermometer demonstration of what can happen on a large scale if no intervention is made. In the midst of this situation, nature arms beings with conditions for changes caused by the hypothalamic action in which all beings of that particular species have a way of surviving, now adapted to the adverse conditions of existence.

The Greeks called it *Physis*, and the Latin priests, without the slightest ability to understand and interpret, through semantics, the holistic meaning of the term, translated it as Nature. What they want to say is that there is an intelligence that surpasses all human understanding, and this same uninterpreted force endowed beings with the capacity for adaptation, knowing that an evolutionary process takes, at best, entire centuries, depending on the species; the greater the life expectancy of an animal, the greater its potential for adaptation, and the opposite is true for evolution, because in a short time it has the possibility of transmitting to its descendants the characteristics that were innovated in its genetic code.

BECAUSE THE SPECIMEN WITH DNA DIFFERENT FROM ITS SPECIES IS, AS A RULE, A MALE

Physis has its own *unique way* of controlling situations that occur in the animal kingdom, and when Charles Darwin developed his hypotheses about the evolution of species, to the point of treating them as theories, he must have, first of all, isolated the *possibility of decline*, in which everything that happens has a logical and defined purpose, *a priori*. In this sense, what seems most intriguing and challenging is to come to the understanding that each sex has a particular responsibility in the perpetuation of the species, with females being responsible for the broad propagation of descendants, in terms of numbers, defined quantitatively, and, in parallel with specific interests, males are responsible for the transmission

of genetic characteristics, whether in terms of production, resistance to pathologies, and other instances. A clear example of this are animals of the *Bos species* (cattle), in which males of the species are responsible for the transmission of 60% of the genetic characteristics, with the remainder being the responsibility of females.

It should be clarified that the transmission of genetic traits has nothing to do with changes in behavior between animals of a given species caused by environmental changes or *stressful situations*, such as abnormal behaviors that occur in confined animals, including humans. Darwin (2015) was categorical in stating that gene mutations occur in species in a generalized manner, throughout the latitudes and longitudes where these specimens live. Acquired behaviors, *a fortiori*, are maintained only as long as the environmental pressure on the specimen in question lasts. Once the negative influence has ceased, the need for such behavior disappears from its existence, and it is not manifest; however, the brain has developed survival strategies that, when necessary, will tend to manifest themselves again. However, this is not a peaceful object of being transmitted via DNA; It may happen that animals born in these same environments and even adult animals that are placed there learn the behaviors adopted by others and, to the observer, it will seem that this was a permanent change in phenotypic characteristics. It comes close to being a change, but it is not permanent, because this is what can be understood as *an epigenetic mutation*.

In an attempt to answer the epigraphic question that opens this topic, the sea turtle will be used as an example, and this choice is due to the fact that this species is the object of study of the co-authors, both of whom are Veterinary Medicine students. Therefore, it should be made clear that when nature prepares its determinations, it aims at the *preservation of the species*, not of the individual in isolation. This issue requires a broader and deeper understanding in order to avoid comparisons with and based on anthropomorphic ideas and any type of identity ideology.

Scientific data is used to arrive at a logical construction that allows the defense of the thesis presented above: A sea turtle lays, on average, 120 eggs. Considering that each male can fertilize a minimum group of 10 females, this would be equivalent to saying that a single specimen could transfer its differentiated genetic code to 1,200 other hatchlings. Considering that, in the environment that has become hostile to animals of this species, there was only one specimen with distinct DNA, the possibility that this genetic code would be perpetuated becomes a plausible reality, something that would be [*almost*] impossible to achieve if this same element of distinction were the privilege of a female.

This situation has already been explained didactically: among sea turtles, only two species reach sexual maturity around 15 years of age, the olive ridley turtle (*Lepidochelys olivacea*) and the hawksbill turtle (*Eretmochelys imbricata*); the others reach sexual maturity around 20 to 30 years of age. Logical thinking applies, in which, starting from the hypothesis that a specific male fertilizes a group of 10 females, he will have the possibility of having 1,200 offspring and, in contrast to this, it is estimated that, of every thousand hatchlings that are born, only one or two reach adulthood, that is, it would take around 15 to 30 years for a single specimen, endowed with a differentiated genetic characteristic and that has proven to be resistant to the hostile, polluted environment that its ancestors inhabit, to be able to pass this capacity for adaptability on to other members of the species. If, hypothetically, this specific characteristic were conferred to a female, it would take a decade for such an effect to supposedly happen, even if betting on the sunset; something that Physis *completely* abhors.

This particular characteristic that accompanies certain specimens within all known animal species , to clarify, a genetic condition different from the entire group, is a phenomenon that guarantees preservation [*and not an aberration of nature*] that is activated when in the presence of some imminent threat. This condition is completely different from the occurrence of epigenetic mutation, in which, in this case, there is adaptability to the stressful environment, as a way of immediately overcoming a situation and, when the pressure is interrupted, everything returns to the natural state of things.

CONCLUSION

Throughout this essay, we sought to understand how epigenetic mutation occurs in animals and what environmental conditions lead to this and how it can be characterized, differing from an evolution within the animal species, the target object of studies. After exploring the hypotheses of changes in the environment, what we have is the condition of animal adaptability being exposed by the hypothalamus, as a means of survival. All care is necessary to avoid giving in to hasty ideas about anthropomorphism, such as that animals have abstract intelligence, which would be to fall into a situation of ridicule and ruin in the academic and scientific community.

Human action has been causing very complex changes in natural environments, which, as a consequence, forces animals in these ecosystems to try to adapt, *a fortiori* , causing bizarre mutations in their behavior and, it is exactly this condition that leads to deeper interpretations about how Biology can explain the principle of the evolution of species.

Through a logical example, it was possible to come closer to a perspective of understanding the possibility of a single animal with DNA distinct from its group exerting influence over all animals of the species, which was taken from sea turtle specimens, the target of scientific studies by the co-authors and taking the Cartesian and positivist model of thought, eliminating any potential for failures, there would be a single descendant in a period varying between 15 and 30 years, according to the species in question. This makes the process of evolution of species something impossible for man to measure, even with the best mathematical and probability models; because natural enemies do not care about the preservation of other species and, in the struggle for survival, very few reach adulthood, becoming capable of leaving descendants.

Understanding that a natural evolution process would represent a possible end to the existence of the species, *Physis* endowed living beings with the ability to adapt to the environment in which they are inserted, modifying their behavior, since this does not require any change in the animal's genetic structure, only the production of new protein chains that respond to the demands of the environment, which was previously pleasant and now hostile. This ability has been conventionally called epigenetic mutation, with the greatest agent causing it being human beings, due to the way in which they interfere with environmental conditions.

Human activity, which causes drastic changes in the environment, has been the cause of epigenetic mutations in animals that are interpreted as true aberrations. The amount of waste from industrialization and material processing procedures releases radioactive materials that, when in their raw form in nature, are not harmful; however, once manipulated, they become aggressive and invasive, deforming the natural structure of animals, forcing them to develop a very strange and, to a certain extent, not understood adaptation system.

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